

Data encodings and algorithms for quantum embedding of data

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Encoding classical data into a quantum is some of the most crucial steps to get to a fully functioning quantum computer but to this day there is no data encoding which is optimal for every use case this paper tries to show different data encodings for different use cases with their advantages and disadvantages the paper also shows algorithms that are used to implement those encodings in reality the paper divides the encoding in two different categories fixed and trainable encodings we discuss both the encoding in detail along with their respective use cases we also discuss about data encoding on NISQ(noisy intermediate quantum) computers the paper also discuss the machine learning approach to quantum embedding of data and its advantages along with its use cases in classification tasks and other machine learning tasks

1. INTRODUCTION

Encoding the data into a quantum computer has become a huge a problem because the algorithms that claim to provide exponential speed-ups over classical computers assume the data can be loaded efficiently ,the loading of data refers to the task of transferring the data that lies on your disk to a controlled environment on which quantum operation can be performed for example a qubit in a quantum computer, data encodings also play a big role in quantum machine learning the types of encoding you use can determine your advantage over classical computers in some modern papers the data encoding is directly being used to solve the problem of classification but there are still problems with training these quantum machine learning models ,the encoding of data into a quantum system can also be seen as a encoding the data into higher dimensions this has clear relation to kernel method from machine learning , the types of data encodings can be broadly

categorised into fixed and trainable data encodings both have their particular uses which we will further discuss in paper the fixed encodings are implemented by circuit that only depends on data, $S(x)$ where x is your feature vector which you want to encode into your quantum system

Fig 0

Where as trainable encodings have tuneable parameters that allow the circuit to embed the data depending on the values of your data as well as your tuneable parameters $S(x, \theta)$ where θ is your vector of tuneable parameters.

When encoding the data into NISQ(noisy intermediate scale quantum computer) There is a huge trade-off between time and space(qubits) the number of qubits we have on a NISQ computer are limited so we need to figure out a scheme which is qubit efficient at least for now but the problem with encodings that take very less space is that the circuits to prepare them take exponential time , the era of NISQ data encoding has this huge trade-off between space and time in rest of the paper will discussing about data encodings and algorithms to implement those encodings with their advantages and disadvantages for different uses cases the rest of the paper is structured as follows SECTION 1 fixed data encodings and algorithms to implement them, SECTION 2 trainable data encoding SECTION 3 conclusion.

2. FIXED DATA ENCODINGS

Fixed data encoding is an encoding scheme where the circuit responsible for the preparation of the quantum state $|\psi\rangle$ that encodes your feature vector x is only dependent on your data. Fixed data encodings tries to embed your data into properties of qubits such as superposition , amplitude or any other-properties

Fig 1

In Fig 2.1 we can see the unitary S that encodes our data into a quantum state is only dependent on data

BASIS ENCODING

The basis encoding follows a trivial idea from computer science and the idea is to represent

the data in binary and if the number is irrational it can be approximated by n bits so if you have a number x it can be approximated by

$$X \approx \sum_{i=0}^{\ell-1} b_i 2^i$$

The b_i here are bits representing 0 or 1 so by this method we can represent X as a vector of these b_i ,this method is simple and is well known and used for almost all of the computation we do on a classical computer we can extend this approach to quantum computers by encoding those b_i into qubits

$$|\psi\rangle = |b_{n-1} \dots b_1 b_0\rangle$$

ALGORITHM: the algorithm to implement basis encoding is pretty simple as the quantum mechanical properties of qubit is not exploited

The state $|\psi\rangle$ can be prepared by applying X-gate on i^{th} qubit if the bit b_i is 1 otherwise if bit b_i is 0 leave the qubit unchanged for example 3 in binary is written as 101 to prepare a state $|101\rangle$ the X-gate can be applied to the first and the third qubit

DISADVANTAGE: Though the circuit is implement basis encoding is of constant depth basis encoding has a huge drawback that is the number of qubit depends on the precion of the approximation l the is the precion of approximation suppose you have X a N -deminsional vector of data points which you want to encode each entry of X is represented by a 64 bit number then the qubits required to encode one data point will be 64 and the qubits required to store X will be $64N$ thus the number of qubits to encode a n -dimensional vector with each of its entries approximated to l bit precision is $O(Nl)$

ADVANTAGE:the basis encoding is some the oldest encodings used in the computer science .It is very easy to perform arithmetic operations on data which was encoded in basis many quantum algorithms that perform arithmetic also assume the basis encoding is being used

AMPLITUDE ENCODING

Amplitude encoding is also known as wavefunction encoding, amplitude encoding tries to use the amplitudes of the quantum state to encode data

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x_i |i\rangle$$

All mod square of the amplitudes must sum up to 1 to follow the rules of quantum mechanics

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} |x_i|^2 = 1$$

ALGORITHM: To this day there is no algorithm that can prepare the exact state above with run time complexity that is polynomial in n the dimension of vector but there are algorithms that can prepare the state $|\psi\rangle$

With some error and have circuit depth polynomial in n which we will later showcase in the paper

ADVANTAGE: the biggest advantage is that the amplitude encoding takes $\log n$ qubits to store a n -dimensional vector giving it the advantage to store a huge amount of data with very few qubits for example with amplitude encoding we can encode a terabyte of data into just 40 qubits cause a terabyte of data is 2^{40} bits so it takes $\log(2^{40})=40$ qubits plus the exact number can be encoded in the amplitudes so there is no approximation like in basis encoding case

DISADVANTAGE: the biggest disadvantage of amplitude encoding is that there is no algorithm that can prepare the state in polynomial time complexity the best algorithm that outputs the exact state are exponential in time complexity also some pre-processing is required to normalize the states

We will further show the algorithm to implement amplitude encoding up to some error but the algorithm cannot be used in

general cases for example the algorithm cannot be used in the places where precision matters and also training the AAE algorithm in practice for large scale quantum computers cannot be done until now

ANGLE ENCODING

the angle encoding tries to encode the data into rotation angles of qubits, a quantum state of a qubit on a Bloch sphere is represented by the following equation

$$|\psi\rangle = \cos\frac{\theta}{2}|0\rangle + e^{i\phi}\sin\frac{\theta}{2}|1\rangle$$

The angle encoding tries to encode the data into rotation angle of qubit

$$|\psi\rangle = \otimes \cos(x_i)|0\rangle + e^{i\phi}\sin(x_i)|1\rangle$$
$$[x_i = \frac{\theta_i}{2}]$$

ALGORITHM: the algorithm to implement it is pretty simple the angle encoding tries to encode data into it can be implemented just by applying a rotation gate around x or y axis the circuit to implement it will be of constant depth as only one rotation gate need to be applied to every qubit if we define a unitary R as follows

$$R = \otimes R_y(x_i)$$

Then by applying R we can get our quantum state $|\psi\rangle$ which encodes our data $R|0 \dots 00\rangle = |\psi\rangle$

ADVANTAGE: it is easy to prepare, the preparation circuit is of constant depth the angle encoding is some of the most widely used encodings in NISQ era because it can encode 1 feature per qubit with the exact precision without requiring extra qubits for precision like basis encoding it is most widely used in quantum machine learning

DISADVANTAGE: the biggest disadvantage is that unlike amplitude encoding it can't encode huge amount of data into very few qubits to

encode a n-dimensional vector angle encoding will require n qubits

DENSE ANGLE ENCODING

The dense angle encoding follows a similar idea to angle encoding but it also tries to utilise the ϕ parameter used to represent the state of the qubits to encode the data

$$|\psi\rangle = \bigotimes_{i=1}^n \cos x_{2i-1} |0\rangle + e^{ix_{2i}} \sin x_i |1\rangle$$

So it is able to encode 2 feature per qubits with requires only n/2 qubits to encode a n-dimensional vector

Thus making it much qubit efficient than angle encoding

GENERAL QUBIT ENCODING

You might ask what is special about the sin and cos function and if you look at the derivation of the bloch sphere there is nothing special about those function except they follow the rules of the quantum mechanics

So we can use any function we want if they follow some rules given below

$$|\psi\rangle = \bigotimes_{i=1}^{\frac{n}{2}} f_i(x_{2i-1}, x_{2i}) |0\rangle + g_i(x_{2i-1}, x_{2i}) |1\rangle$$

Where $f, g : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ such that $|f_i|^2 + |g_i|^2 = 1 \forall i$

these function also decides the amplitudes so the mod square of these functions should sum up-to one

QRAM

QRAM is a theoretical way to get access to data in practical scenario implementing QRAM is at least till now is not possible there is lot of work going on to build a efficient error free QRAM but to this day there are no efficient version of

QRAM published checkout references for more work on QRAM now let us see how QRAM works theoretically

QRAM as the name reflects works on the principle of ram you provide it with the address and it puts the data from the address into a specific register but it has a quantum property called superposition you can give the address register a superposition of addresses and it will give all the data from those addresses in superposition into an output register

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{m}} \sum_{i=1}^m |a\rangle_i |0\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{m}} \sum_{i=1}^m |a\rangle_i |x\rangle_i$$

here $|a\rangle_i$ is taking superposition of addresses and QRAM returns the data stored in those addresses in the ancillary register in superposition

ALGORITHM: to this day there is no efficient practical implementation of QRAM done

ADVANTAGE: it only takes log n+1 to encode the address is very efficient if we can build it in practice lot of theoretical work in the field assume you have a working QRAM cause it makes the analysis a ton easier

DISADVANTAGE: the biggest disadvantage is that the implementation of QRAM we have today takes exponential time to run building a working QRAM is still a active area of research

QUAM

You might say we have used some properties of a qubit to encode data there is one very important characteristic of a quantum mechanical system that is it can be in superposition in QUAM encoding we encode the data in the state of superposition

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} |x_i\rangle$$

ALGORITHM: there is a well known algorithm by ventura ,martiniz that implements QRAM with just $2n+1$ qubits the algorithm is bug so we will later showcase in the paper

ADAVANTAGE: the biggest advantage of the QUAM is that it can encode the data in basis encoding which can be used in arithmetic processing plus the number of qubits required to encode a n-dimensional vector with each of its each of its entries approximated to l bit precision is $O(l)$ so it is very efficient and lot of current algorithm uses this encoding in some way or other

DISADVANTAGE: to recover the full data stored in the superposition we need to measure it at least n times but then also not guaranteed that you will get the full data back

This can be seen in the algorithm that solves linear system of equations called HHL algorithm

ALGORITHMS FOR QUAM AND AMPLITUDE ENCODING

as we have said above the paper covers algorithms to implement QUAM encoding and amplitude encode the references of these original papers can be found in the references

AAE

AAE is a approximation algorithm that encodes the data into quantum states using amplitude encoding with some error and uses PQC(parametrized quantum circuits) it is more like a machine learning approach ,so lets us define what should be the goal of AAE should be to prepare the following state

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x_i |i\rangle \quad (1)$$

The goal of AAE is to prepare this above where x_i are the data points of a vector X so AAE tries

to find a unitary that it can train and at the end apply to get the desired state

$$U(\theta)|0 \dots 00\rangle = |data\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x_i |i\rangle \quad (2)$$

Now lets us remember the mod square of the x_i correspond to the probability of measuring the state $|i\rangle$ on measurement so we want to design a unitary U such that

$$|\langle i|U(\theta)|0\rangle|^2 = x_i^2 \quad \forall i \quad (3)$$

The above equation corresponds to the probability of starting in state $|0\rangle$ and applying $U(\theta)$ and measuring the state $|i\rangle$

There is one more condition we need to satisfy to get perfect encoding

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle i|H^{\otimes}U(\theta)|0\rangle|^2 &= \left[\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} x_i \langle i|H^{\otimes}|k\rangle \right]^2 \\ &= (x_i^H)^2 \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

NOTE: that x^H can be computed in $O(N \log N)$ by using walsh-hadamard transform and the bound can be improved in the special cases

if the condition (3) and (4) are satisfied then equation (2) will be satisfied the proof is given in [5], NOTE: this approach only works if all x_i are positive or negative but the algorithm can be modified to work also in mixed case of positive and negative x_i and is showed in paper [5]

now we need to optimise the parameterised circuit $U(\theta)$ so it satisfy those conditions the first thing we need to do is to define the cost function which tells us how to update the parameters, AAE uses a well known cost function for probability distributions called MND(maximum mean disperancy) written in its kernel form

$$\mathcal{L}_{MND}(q,\theta,p) = \gamma_{MND}(q,\theta,p)^2$$

$$\gamma_{MND} = \left| \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} q_{\theta}(j)\Phi(j) - \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} p(j)\Phi(j) \right|$$

Where q_{θ} model probability distribution and $p(j)$ is the desired probability distribution and where $\Phi(j)$ is a function that maps j to a feature space. Thus, given the kernel $\kappa(j, k)$ as $\kappa(j, k) = \Phi(k)^T \Phi(j)$ it holds

$$\gamma_{MMD} = E_{k \sim p_{\theta}} [k(k, j)] - 2E_{\substack{k \sim p \\ j \sim q_{\theta}}} [k(k, j)] + E_{\substack{k \sim p \\ j \sim p}} [k(k, j)]$$

Where for example if the expectation value for one example is defined as follows

$$E_{\substack{k \sim q_{\theta} \\ j \sim q_{\theta}}} = \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} K(j, k) q_{\theta}(j) q_{\theta}(k)$$

Note that, even though the index of the sum goes till $N - 1$ in Eq. (13), we can efficiently estimate the expectation value without $O(N)$ computation by sample averaging as follows. First, given N^{shot} as the number of samples for each index, we sample $\{j_{\ell}\}_{\ell=1}^{N^{shot}-1} = 0$ and $\{k_{\ell}\}_{\ell=1}^{N^{shot}-1} = 0$ according to the probability distribution $q_{\theta}(\cdot)$; note that, in our case, $q_{\theta}(j)$ is the probability to obtain $q_{\theta}(j)$ as a result of measuring the final state of PQC, and thus we can obtain samples just by measuring the final state multiple times. Then, using the samples $\{j_{\ell}\}_{\ell=1}^{N^{shot}-1} = 0$ and $\{k_{\ell}\}_{\ell=1}^{N^{shot}-1} = 0$, we can approximate the expectation value as

$$E_{\substack{k \sim p_{\theta} \\ j \sim q_{\theta}}} [k(k, j)] = \frac{1}{N^{shot}} \sum_{j, k=0}^{N^{shot}-1} k(j, k)$$

It is proven in the paper [5] that the cost function can be minimized by using a algorithm called the gradient decent and the depth of the circuit will be polynomial in n the algorithm can approximate the q_{θ} with $O(1/N^{shot})$ error

QUAM ENCODING

We will see the algorithm for QUAM encoding shown in [8] by Ventura and Martinez the algorithm is quite simple and runs in polynomial time with using only two and three qubit gates the algorithm prepares a superposition of states with the data encoded in binary form

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} |x_i\rangle$$

Where $x_i \in \{0,1\}^n$ now let us first define the operators that the algorithm will use

$$\hat{S}^p = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \sqrt{(p-1)/p} & -1/\sqrt{p} \\ 0 & 0 & 1/\sqrt{p} & \sqrt{(p-1)/p} \end{bmatrix}$$

This operator breaks the state the into two parts each with probability amplitude $1/\sqrt{p}$ and $1/\sqrt{1-p}$

Where $1 < p < m$ these operators form a set of conditional transfers that will be used to incorporate the set of patterns into a coherent quantum state, There will be a different \hat{S}^p

Operator associated with each pattern to be stored next define

$$\hat{F} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Which flips the state of a qubit, and the 2-qubit Control-not operator

$$\hat{F}^0 = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{F} & \hat{0} \\ \hat{0} & \hat{I}_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Where $\hat{0}$ and \hat{I}_2 are the 2x2 zero and identity matrices respectively, which conditionally flips the state of the second qubit if the first qubit is in the state $|0\rangle$ these are the gates that acts on two qubits now let us define the gates which acts on three qubits the first one of which is

$$\hat{A}^{00} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{F} & \hat{0} \\ \hat{0} & \hat{I}_6 \end{bmatrix}$$

The operator above flips the third qubit if the first second qubits are zero now let us explore the main algorithm that transforms the state into $A|0 \dots 00\rangle = |\psi\rangle$

Now suppose you want to encode a set of state into a superposition lets call them $z = \{x_i \dots x_2, x_1\}$ where $x_i \in \{0,1\}^n \forall i$

So you want algorithm that prepares the state

$$A|0 \dots 00\rangle = |\psi\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} |x_i\rangle$$

The algorithm to produce the state is given in Fig 2 below

1. Generate $|\tilde{f}\rangle = |x_1 \dots x_n, g_1 \dots g_{n-1}, c_1 c_2\rangle = |\bar{0}\rangle$
2. for $m \geq p \geq 1$
3. for $1 \leq j \leq n$
4. if $z_{pj} \neq z_{p+1j}$ (where $z_{m+1} = \{0\}^n$)
5. $\hat{F}_{c_2 x_j}^0 |\tilde{f}\rangle$
6. $\hat{F}_{c_2 c_1}^0 |\tilde{f}\rangle$
7. $\hat{S}_{c_1 c_2}^p |\tilde{f}\rangle$
8. $\hat{A}_{x_1 x_2 g_1}^{z_1 z_2} |\tilde{f}\rangle$
9. for $3 \leq k \leq n$
10. $\hat{A}_{x_k g_{k-2} g_{k-1}}^{z_k} |\tilde{f}\rangle$
11. $\hat{F}_{g_{n-1} c_1}^1 |\tilde{f}\rangle$
12. for $n \geq k \geq 3$
13. $\hat{A}_{x_k g_{k-2} g_{k-1}}^{z_k} |\tilde{f}\rangle$
14. $\hat{A}_{x_1 x_2 g_1}^{z_1 z_2} |\tilde{f}\rangle$

Fig. 2. Quantum algorithm for storing patterns.

Now let us explore the algorithm line by line before we start we should know that algorithm have 3 registers the x, g, and c the x register have n qubits and g register has n-1 qubits and

the c register has 2 qubits so the qubits needed by the algorithm is 2n-1 but later half of the qubits can be discarded as x register is used to store the superposition of the state and it contains data the g register is used as a temporary register and the c register is used as a flag. the algorithm starts by initializing all of its registers to the zero state note that the line 3-6 corresponds to flipping the state and 8-14 corresponds to saving the state the algorithms first for any state whose c_2 is $|0\rangle$ the qubits in the x register corresponding to the non-zero bits in the first x_i will be flipped and then the c_1 qubits state is flipped if the c_2 state is in $|0\rangle$. this flipping of c_1 state marks this state for being operated upon by S operator in the next step next the algorithm applies the S operator which splits the state with p=number of x_i

Corresponding to the Probability amplitudes next step of the algorithm saves the states with the smaller probability amplitude and then the algorithm repeats the same process for next x_i

Now let us see an example let our state to encode be $z = \{01, 10, 11\}$

Initially $|\psi\rangle = |0..0, 0..0, 00\rangle$ where the commas separate the three registers now the algorithm starts for $x_0 = 10$ the algorithm flips the qubits in the x register according to the first non zero bits in the x_i controlled by the c_2 qubit and then it flips the qubit c_1 controlled by the qubit c_2 which correspond to line 3-6 in the algorithm

$$|00..0, 00..0, 00\rangle \xrightarrow{FLIP} |01, 0, 10\rangle$$

Now line 7 applies the \hat{S}^p operator which creates the superposition of states with amplitudes amplitude $1/\sqrt{p}$ and $1/\sqrt{1-p}$ with p=number of x_i

$$\hat{S}^p \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} |01, 0, 11\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} |01, 0, 10\rangle$$

Now the algorithm save the states by making the state with smaller amplitude permanent

and flipping its c_1 qubit and resetting the other state to repeat the process

$$save \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|01,0,01\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}|01,0,00\rangle$$

the algorithm repeat itself on the state whose c_2 qubit is in the state zero and follows the same procedure for another x_i

now let us see another iteration of algorithm for $x_2 = 10$

$$flip \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|01,0,01\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}|10,0,10\rangle$$

Next the algorithm will operator \hat{S}^p to create the superposition

$$\hat{S}^p \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|01,0,01\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}|10,0,11\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}|10,0,10\rangle$$

Now the algorithm saves the state with smaller coefficient and resets the other states for another iteration for the next x_i

save \rightarrow

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|01,0,01\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}|10,0,01\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}|10,0,00\rangle$$

The algorithm iterates this repetition for all x_i at the end of the algorithm we should get the state

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|01,0,01\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|10,0,01\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|11,0,01\rangle$$

As you can see the g and the c register is of no use now and all are in the same state so we can trace out the c and the g register leaving us with the desired superposition of data

$$A|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|01\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|10\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|11\rangle$$

There can be a difference in sign but they can be corrected by some error correction methods

2. TRAINABLE DATA ENCODING

So far we have looked the encodings which only uses the properties of quantum mechanical system (qubits) to encode the data and these were only dependent on the data

these have their own application but when looking in the field of the quantum machine learning the goal is to predict the class or label of a data point these encoding does not work because these encoding of data do the work to place the data point on the bloch sphere and once it is placed the machine learning algorithm can only try to find a boundary that separates the data but if the data was placed in a manner that it was inseparable the goal of the machine learning algorithm can never be achieved

Figure 3-inseparable data on the bloch sphere

The red line above shows the decision boundary as we can see trying to separate the blue and black data points is very difficult and sometimes impossible and now all a quantum machine learning algorithm can do is to rotate this decision boundary around if we use fixed data encoding we don't have control over these type of situations as it depends on the data so we need encoding that also depend on some trainable parameters so these type of conditions does not occur so we try to use angle encoding that also depends on some trainable parameters θ there are some ansatz that work very well for training quantum encoding and QAOA is one of them

Now let us see what is the goal of a quantum machine learning algorithm and that is to verify the data points into correct classes as we have seen the data encoding places the points on the Bloch sphere we can use it to our advantage by placing the data points from different classes far apart so we can easily differentiate those points so the goal our encoding should be to maximize the distance between data points from different classes and minimizing the distance of data points that have same class so we need to find the trainable parameters θ that can achieve this type of encoding for that we need to define the cost function which achieves the goal described above can be written in terms of distance measure

$$C = 1 - \frac{1}{2}(tr\sigma^2 + tr\rho^2 - tr\rho\sigma)$$

Where ρ and σ are two density operators which are ensemble of data points that belong to different class (state of two different clusters) the terms in C have intuitive meaning the term $tr\rho\sigma$ refers to distance between two ensembles and terms $tr\sigma^2$ and $tr\rho^2$ refers to intra-cluster distance which holds the cluster together

MEASUREMENTS

Now once we have encoded the data onto the Bloch sphere in well-organized clusters according to their classes its time to predict we can predict the new data point x by encoding it onto the Bloch sphere and measuring the its distance from each cluster and we can say it belongs to the class from which it is closer to there are measurement you can take that tells you how different two states are and the optimal one is the Helstrom measurement it can optimally tell the how much different two states are but yet on the NISQ computers we cannot use the algorithm that performs the Helstrom measurement because of the qubit and time complexity of the algorithm but we can use other measurement which a quantum

computer can perform easily fidelity is one those measurement the fidelity measurement tells the similarity between two states the fidelity for our use is given by

$$f_{fid}(x) = \langle x | \rho - \sigma | x \rangle$$

The fidelity assigns x to ρ if the state x is more similar to ρ than σ and vice versa the fidelity measurement can be implemented on

A quantum computer either by a SWAP or inversion test so by using fidelity measurement we can determine which class does x belong from

DISADVANTAGES

The idea of these quantum machine learning algorithms seems quite useful but in reality training these PCQ is not a easy job there are many major problems that have no perfect solutions to them some problems include like barren plateau problem in which the gradient of the cost function start to become exponentially flat as we grow the size of the circuit this is quite a major problem because without completely solving it the idea of the PCQ is not scalable at all another problem with training PCQ is that landscape of your cost function could have a many local minima the optimizer can easily get stuck in those local minima and never reach to the optimal minimum there are solutions proposed to all these problems but further studies are needed to show the validity of these methods

3. CONCLUSION

In this paper we talked about various data encoding techniques along with their disadvantages and advantages we also discussed the fixed and trainable encodings both of them have their own uses while fixed encoding is suitable for algorithm the trainable encoding is essential for quantum machine learning we also discussed an approximation

algorithm that uses PCQ to prepare the state with amplitude encoding to encode the data but the algorithm cannot be used in the places where the exact or very precise data need to be loaded then we discussed the algorithm for QUAM encoding the QUAM encoding is a very useful encoding and many well-known algorithms can be modified to work in this encoding the algorithm can encode the data in its precise form can and we can do arithmetic operations on the data easily because the data is encoded in the binary form then the paper covered the trainable data encoding which are used for classification tasks they map to the data points on the bloch sphere in clusters according to their classes then paper covered measurement which can be used to predict the label of a new data point but the problem with the idea of the these trainable encodings is that they are not very easy to train there are several issues in training them the area of embedding the data into a quantum system is still an active area of research and whether there exist an optimal data encoding for all tasks is still and open question

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